

THE IMPORTANCE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN IMPROVING ACCOUNTING

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Abstract. *This article describes the actual changes taking place in the accounting system in the conditions of the digital economy, as well as the importance of economic entities introducing new digital management technologies, gaining an advantage in the competitive environment and forming. The essence of the concept of the digital economy and the advantages and disadvantages of using software and blockchain technologies that are currently being used for accounting in our country have been studied.*

The concept of digital economy has been approached differently in different sources. For the first time, the term "digital economy" was introduced into practice by the American programmer Nicholas Negroponte in 1995, but now the term is widely used all over the world^[4].

Keywords: *digital economy, telecommunication technologies, strategic features of industry development, software, digital information, accounting automation.*

Introduction. The issue of the use of modern Information Technology in its activities is becoming more and more important in modern accounting. The development of the digital economy, calculated from the current innovations of all network service personnel, requires further improvement of modern information and telecommunications technologies, while these innovations form more new opportunities and requirements for accounting ^[5,8].

One such innovation is the study of the importance of digital technologies in improving accounting, and it is precisely in the context of the transition to a digital economy that the laying of this issue is considered to study the importance of digital technologies on the basis of economic assumptions and draw conclusions for their application to practice.

Relevance of the topic. The law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On accounting" of April 14, 2016 [1] has become the legal basis for familiarization with perfect and reliable economic data, which is considered one of the foundations of modern management.

Modernization and diversification of economic sectors, radical increase of the role of small business and private entrepreneurship in the economy[9], modernization rates in the economy of our country are provided by reforms carried out as a result of automation of accounting in the digital economy.

A number of regulatory documents have been adopted by our government on the process of transition to the digital economy. In particular, on approval of the strategy of the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 6079 "Digital Uzbekistan-2030" dated October 5, 2020, the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 4699 "On measures for the wide introduction of digital economy and e-government" on April 28, 2020 laid the foundation for the further development of the digital economy in our country.

As our head of state Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev noted, "in order to achieve progress, it is necessary and crucial for us to master digital knowledge and modern information

technologies. This gives us the opportunity to go the shortest path of ascent"[3] that our non-deviant implementation of their thoughts brings us closer to the digital economy even faster.

The topic of digitization of our economy has become one of the pressing issues in our country today. It is for this reason that it is an important issue to increase the efficiency of the programs, sites and technologies used in modern accounting in the conditions of this economy, as well as the effective use of solutions, innovative ideas, applied to practice using existing opportunities, their implementation as a strategic idea.

First of all, it is important to say that in the context of digital economy, information in digital form is becoming a key element of all spheres from day to day, and at the same time, in the accounting areas, too, increasing the reliability of information in maintaining the accounting system leads to an increase in the reliability of the attraction of external capital to enterprises, this in turn leads to the service of ensuring the stability of the economy.

Research methodology. The research process used methods of logical reasoning, systematic approach, sample observation, comparison, and correlation-regression analysis. The purpose of the article is to talk about the role of accounting in enterprises in the conditions of a digital economy, about important aspects in the digitization of the accounting industry, as well as about specific information about their situation, which should be paid serious attention to.

Analysis and results. The system for the study of scientific literature and the implementation of economic, cultural and social relations through digital technologies is precisely the system of digital economy, according to our first scientific results or mature economic scientists. Sometimes this economy, new economy or internet economy is sometimes defined by the term web economy ^[13].

Based on our concepts in the results of learning, we can come to the idea that digital economy is such an activity in which the results obtained from the processing of large statistics are understood in modern images in short and simple views to be accurately, intelligibly automated to use. If we carry out research data using such methods as digital economy, modern economic-mathematical modeling now for processing in the requirements of technologies, correlation-regression analysis, we are considered to have gone close to digital technology, since the methods also require ingenuity, innovative thinking.

Using the results obtained, the above methods, the study is considered to be a factor in shaping information in a digital format, which makes it possible to modernize the processes in the activity of the object, automate the processes of optimization of equipment and technologies, production, service, storage of products, sale and delivery to consumers based on information received from the results.

Assuming that business is taken as an object when Strategic Development, Bank competitiveness indicators, value-added creation, etc. are studied in research, it is inevitable that our results obtained if the elements of digital economy and technology are applied and analyzed in economic and mathematical methods will now become the results of scientific research in demand of the time ^[7].

In turn, the development of digital economy will further require the improvement of modern information and telecommunications technologies, which will create new scientifically based requirements, opportunities for accounting, which are using current programs and technologies^[10].

The application of the elements of digital economy in all processes, the human factor, by reducing the sphere of influence and automating the processes that are expected to be carried out, leads to a new formation, modernization of the competitiveness of entrepreneurs, production and management.

At the same time, the modernization of production and management in almost all sectors and sectors in a market economy, a technical and technological revision, a large-scale implementation of new equipment measures will lead to an expansion of the possibilities for the production of competitive products. The high-speed development of the world economy and its features require a professional approach to digital technology in the activities of all types of enterprises.

Today, the main technical means of information processing technology are personal laptops and computers[11]. In many organizations, accounting widely uses software products designed specifically for convenient storage of information, analysis of accounting data, creation of documents and reports. [12].

They allow accountants in an organization to manage interconnected accounting departments and provide management opportunity for executive employees to access and manage important information. Automation of accounting in organizations facilitates the work of accountants, and an error in the manual processing of information eliminates shortcomings.

In particular, the application of digitization in the field of accounting creates the following advantages:

- data turnover accelerates;
- increased reliability of data;
- labor efficiency increases in the field;
- excess time in filling out documents is saved;
- the cost of the product is calculated in high accuracy;
- it is possible to process large amounts of data at short opportunities;
- quick adaptability to changes in adopted regulatory documents;
- flexibility to maintain reports based on international standards;
- the absence of various deviations in taxes and payments to the budget.

As noted above, digitization of accounting provides enterprises with great opportunities.

Digitalization of accounting, in addition to the above advantages in the field, also creates the following serious and problematic situations:

- As a result of network automation, the number of jobs can be reduced;
- Significant information may be revealed as a result of data leakage from the network;
- increased attention to software;

Interruptions or temporary interruptions in the Internet Network cause some shortcomings in the system.

Conclusions and suggestions. In conclusion, digital technologies are important in the creation and maintenance of a database. When conducting enterprise accounting, high accuracy will be needed, and the use of elements of digital technology will help to minimize errors and reduce the importance of its correction, jobs and tools. The application of elements of digital technology to processes allows you to quickly formulate and control reports, ensure a quick circulation of products, financial data and documents, correctly and accurately formulate

accounting and tax reports, and increase the time-saving accuracy in all processes related to accounting.

Today, all online accounting operas, banks and information technology portfolios are used in the daily activities of an accountant, relying on digital technologies in the storage and processing of data in the capabilities of cloud technologies.

These changes in the economy will also begin a new way of working accounting, for which it will be necessary for economist scientists and practitioners to study based on proposals, the formation of their model in the conditions of the digital economy based on a new algorithm of work, legislation, regulatory documents, accounting guidelines and rules.

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